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“THE LOVE THAT STAYED”

I pushed you back, I walked away,
and let my fears decide the day;
I spoke harsh words I now regret,
but still you chose not to forget.

You stood through storms I could not name,
through pain, through doubt, through silent blame;
you held my heart with patient hands,
and taught me love that understands.

Then July came, and love was clear,
I chose the one who stayed so near;
you became my peace, my answered prayer,
my safest place, my truest care.

Now every bloom my heart can show
was born from love that chose to grow;
and all my life will speak of you,
Mr. KJ, my love so true.

